

THE ROLE OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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One of the most important strategic factors in achieving the required level of life support for the population and successful economic development is the formation and functioning of modern entrepreneurship in the economic space. Entrepreneurship is the main element of a market economy, without which the country's economy cannot develop stably. The entrepreneur and entrepreneurship are the driving forces of the market process, performing its main constructive functions.

The article discusses the prospects for the development of youth entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. Youth entrepreneurship is defined as a tool that ensures employment growth, the involvement of young people in economic activities, their socialization and self-realization. The development of this institute makes it possible to use the creative potential of the younger generation in the interests of innovative development of the country.

Youth is the most promising category of the labor force. The younger generation, as a rule, is distinguished by creative thinking, which turns out to be an advantageous characteristic for entrepreneurial activity, ensuring competitiveness in the business field. Youth is the engine of innovation, modern technology and economic development. Her full support is the basis of the state's youth policy. This year is aimed at stimulating entrepreneurship among young people and

creating conditions for the successful development of small and medium-sized businesses.

One of the main goals of establishing a socially oriented market economy in Uzbekistan is the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country. To achieve this goal, economic reforms were carried out and major institutional frameworks were created to enhance its role. These include business organizations and legal documents guaranteeing them, public organizations and enterprises that provide assistance to entrepreneurs.

The formation of a complex of private entrepreneurship and small businesses in Uzbekistan is progressing successfully. Enterprises engaged in small business activities independently of the state, that is, without large capital expenditures, can create jobs themselves, reduce the shortage of temporarily available goods, and even eliminate this shortage completely. In our current society, it is necessary to direct the activities of small businesses to meet the needs of some people. This is clearly visible in the spheres of consumer services and the production of consumer goods. Small businesses are also very important for technological innovation.

The concept of long-term socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period until 2030 sets the following goal of the state youth policy: creating conditions for the successful socialization and effective self-realization of youth, developing the potential of youth and its use in the interests of the innovative development of the country, implementing programs to support youth entrepreneurship, in including in innovative sectors of the economy [1].

The Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy outlines tasks to ensure employment of young people and achieve solutions to their problems, as well as to reduce the unemployment rate from 14 to 11 percent. At the same time, attention was paid to further popularizing the IT sector among young people and increasing the export of related services. To achieve this, effective measures have been planned to ensure employment of 300 thousand young people in this segment, train schoolchildren in modern professions in demand in the international IT market, expand the “One

Million Programmers” project and annually train 15 thousand gifted boys and girls based on programs in accordance with the requirements of prestigious international organizations.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to investing in human capital, which, due to changes occurring in the global economy, is becoming particularly relevant. State support makes it easier for young entrepreneurs to enter the market. The youth entrepreneurship support system is made up of bodies and structures at the federal, regional and local levels. The effectiveness of this system is ensured by setting a common goal, defining common tasks, a well-thought-out legislative and regulatory framework, establishing organizational and legal relations and acting within the framework of common methodological approaches.

One of the main ways to strengthen the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its comprehensive development, and accelerate the transition of the economy, especially to the market, is the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship. Therefore, a number of laws, decrees and resolutions were adopted on the development of entrepreneurship, its support by the state, initiatives in private entrepreneurship, and its encouragement [2]. In accordance with the decree of the head of our state dated April 21, 2021, youth industrial and entrepreneurial zones are being created in all regions of our country, in which favorable conditions are created for youth business.

The strategic priority of state youth policy is to create conditions for the formation of a harmonious, constantly improving, erudite, competitive, caring personality, with a strong moral core, capable of adapting to changing conditions and receptive to new creative ideas. 210 entrepreneurial and industrial youth zones have been created in the republic. Huge funds are allocated to ensure her employment, and appropriate platforms are created. Work in this direction has several goals.

First, supporting the development of youth entrepreneurship stimulates economic growth. Helps boys and girls implement their ideas, develop business projects and more.

Secondly, the organization of youth industrial and enterprise zones attracts domestic and foreign investment. In turn, location of production and business in such zones contributes to the economic development of the territories.

Thirdly, MPZs are also platforms for the introduction of new technologies, the development of innovative products and certain services, and therefore, increasing the country's competitiveness in the world market.

Fourthly, the development of such business territories serves to create jobs for young citizens, reduce unemployment, strengthen social sustainability, and improve living conditions of the population.

The main areas of state support for youth entrepreneurship are:

1. involving young people in entrepreneurial activities;
2. providing assistance in finding employment for young people in the areas of small and medium-sized businesses;
3. providing assistance in the promotion of innovative projects of young entrepreneurs;
4. financial and property support for young businesses;
5. assistance in improving the level of education and qualifications of youth entrepreneurship.

Involvement in entrepreneurial activity is one of the solutions for the younger generation to the problem of employment, which has become especially acute in the regions of the country during the crisis period of economic development. Youth entrepreneurship helps strengthen the financial situation of young people, as well as their professional and personal self-realization, transformation of the economy, as well as the relevance of managing the process of social adaptation of youth, involving them in creative activities and providing opportunities for maximum personal self-realization, it can be argued that the mechanism for supporting and developing youth entrepreneurship is a central element in solving the problems of socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan [3].

As practice shows, young entrepreneurs can respond to new economic opportunities and trends much faster. For example, youth with technical education, youth are capable of accelerating the digital economy through disruptive startups. But, unfortunately, most young people do not know how to realize their ambitions in this direction due to relatively limited knowledge and insufficient experience, possible risks, insufficient motivation, small available capital, etc. Therefore, stimulating and developing youth entrepreneurship is one of priority tasks of modernizing the state economy in modern conditions.

Today's young entrepreneurs are the result of New Uzbekistan. They have new knowledge and approaches. Therefore, industrial zones must be handed over to the youth. This will be a ready-made “project factory” for districts. Those in charge should only help businesses innovate and enter the market. The main thing is cost, quality, competition,” said Shavkat Mirziyoyev [4].

From June 1, 2024, “Young Entrepreneur” competitions will held in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Their organization, as well as the competitive selection of promising business projects and ideas of young people at the level of mahallas, districts, regions and the republic, will be carried out by the Agency for Youth Affairs. Particular attention will be paid to the ideas of young entrepreneurs with special needs.

The phenomenon of youth entrepreneurship describes the process by which creative and innovative ideas are transformed into enterprises initiated and managed by young people. Active development of their own business is the best thing that ambitious young people can do for their personal and professional development in particular, as well as for the state as a whole. This opens up great opportunities for them for professional and career growth and sets them the goal of becoming creators of their own future [5].

To sum up, youth has always played an important role in the formation and development of civil society. Therefore, our country pays special attention to comprehensive support and stimulation of its active participation in the socio-economic development of the state. Thus, declaring 2024 the Year of Support for

Youth and Business indicates recognition of the importance of the younger generation in domestic political processes, because human capital is a key factor in economic growth, innovation, sustainable development and improving the well-being of the population. After all, a qualified workforce is able to effectively usage investment resources in the areas of healthcare, education, science and technology.

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